

The Chemistry of the Lower Valent Iodides of Gallium

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Complexes of gallium di-iodide have been prepared and studied. All the compounds are of the form $\text{GaL}_4^+ \text{GaI}_4^-$, where L is a monodentate ligand attachment. GaI_2 is thus concluded to be structurally analogous to the corresponding chloride and bromide, being $\text{Ga}^+ \text{GaI}_4^-$.

Attempts have been made to prepare complexes of gallium monoiodide, $\text{GaL}_4^+ \text{I}^-$. The products isolated from the reactions between ligands and GaI are always "divalent" $\text{GaL}_4^+ \text{GaI}_4^-$, gallium metal being produced as a result of the disproportionation.

In recent years compounds of gallium with apparent oxidation numbers of less than three for the metal have been extensively studied'. The 'dichloride' and 'dibromide' have been shown by X-ray² spectra³ studies to be salts $\text{Ga}^+ \text{GaCl}_4^-$ and $\text{Ga}^+ \text{GaBr}_4^-$ respectively. In contrast, the other 'divalent' compounds GaS and GaSe have been shown by X-ray studies⁴ to contain Ga-Ga bonds.

No structural investigations on gallium di-iodide have been reported and the present work has been carried out in an attempt to establish whether the compound is chemically similar to the other dihalides or to the corresponding chalcogenides. Electronegativity considerations would classify iodine⁵ (2.5) with sulphur (2.5) and selenium (2.4) rather than with bromine (2.8) or chlorine (3.0).

In the present communication, the chemical behaviour of gallium di-iodide and gallium sulphide with a wide range of oxygen, nitrogen or sulphur donors has been investigated. In no case did reaction occur with GaS , even after the compound and the ligand had been refluxed together for over a week. Gallium di-iodide did react with all the ligands studied to provide complexes of stoichiometry Ga_nL_n , where L is a monodentate ligand or one complexing site of a polydentate ligand.

All the compounds are white, except the dithizone derivative which is purple. These are all slowly decomposed by moist air, those with polydentate ligands being less sensitive than those with monodentate ligands.

Where solubility of the complexes permitted, molecular weight and conductivity measurements in nitrobenzene were carried out. In the case of the molecular weights, high accuracy could not be achieved, since even in the most favourable circumstances the solubility of the complex was relatively low. The molar conductivity measurements

1. Greenwood, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1963, 5, 91.

2. Garton and Powell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1957, 4, 84.

3. Woodward, Garton and Roberts, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1956, 3723; Woodward, Greenwood, Hall and Worrall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1923; 1958, 1505.

4. Hahn and Frank, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1955, 278, 340; Tatarinova Aulcitor, Yu and Pinaker, *Kristallografiya*, 1956, 1, 537.

5. Pauling, "Nature of the Chemical Bond", Oxford Univ. Press, London, 3rd ed., 1960, p. 90.

gave values of 21.3 ± 1.4 mhos for all the compounds studied. This indicates that the compounds are all 1 : 1 electrolytes, and the value may be compared with those of complexes of $\text{Ga}_2\text{Cl}_4^{6,7}$ and Ga_2Br_4 which were 20 ± 2.5 mhos. The value is also close to those reported by Foss and Gibson⁸ and Kabesh and Nyholm⁹ for other 1 : 1 electrolytes. These data, together with the molecular weight measurements, show that complexes of GaI_2 are of the form $[\text{GaL}_4]^+ [\text{GaI}_4]^-$, and in this are entirely comparable with those of the other halides.

The chemical similarity between GaI_2 and the other dihalides and its extreme difference in reactivity from GaS suggest that it should be formulated as $\text{Ga}^+\text{GaI}_4^-$. The structural difference between GaS and GaI_2 is probably related to the valency of the anion since the occurrence of a gallium bond in the former but not in the latter is clearly not simply a consequence of the electronegativity of the anion. It is perhaps relevant that in $\text{Ga}^+ \text{GaI}_4^-$ the gallium (III) entity is displaying the usual co-ordination number of four, whereas in a species $\text{Ga}^+ \text{GaS}_4^-$ the gallium (III) species would only be showing a co-ordination number of two.

Some purely monovalent complexes of gallium have been previously isolated as a result of disproportionation of gallium (II) compounds⁷, $[\text{GaL}_4]^+ [\text{GaX}_4]^- \rightarrow [\text{GaL}_4]^+ \text{X}^- + \text{GaX}_3$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br , $\text{L}=\text{dioxan}$, morpholine or acetylaceton). No tendency for such a reaction was found for $[\text{GaL}_4]^+ [\text{GaI}_4]^-$ complexes and it was decided to attempt to prepare purely monovalent gallium complexes from GaI . When the ligand was added to the solid at the room temperature no reaction occurred. On refluxing, reaction did take place slowly but produced gallium metal together with the 'divalent' product:

This result is surprising. The reason may be ascribed to slow disproportionation of gallium monoiodide at the temperature employed. Certainly, above 300° the decomposition

occurs very rapidly. The failure to obtain simple monovalent gallium complexes may perhaps be a result of kinetic rather than thermodynamic factors.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of gallium Di-iodide.—Calculated quantities of gallium and iodine were heated in an evacuated sealed tube at $420\text{--}450^\circ$ in a horizontal furnace for 15 hr. The deep-red viscous liquid formed at this temperature was very slowly allowed to run into a constricted portion of the tube and left behind some unchanged gallium. It solidified on cooling to an orange-yellow solid. The tube was opened in a dry box and the contents transferred to another Carius tube and sealed under vacuum. One end of this tube was heated at 165° and the other end cooled with compressed air to sublime any GaI_3 from the product.

On a 12 g. scale yields of greater than 90% were obtained. (Found: Ga , 22.9; I , 78.3. Calc. Ga , 21.5; I , 78.3%).

The solubility of GaI_2 in benzene at 20° was found to be 1.56 g./100 g.

6. All, Brewer, Chadwick and Garton, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, 9, 124.

7. Brewer, Chadwick and Garton, *Ibid.* 1961, 23, 45.

8. Foss and Gibson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 3063.

9. Kabesh and Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 38.

Preparation of Gallium Monoiodide.—It was prepared by an analogous route to that used for gallium di-iodide. A red liquid was formed and was slowly tipped in the sealed tube from any insoluble matter. It was then rapidly cooled with compressed air. The solid was fawn coloured and analysed to $\text{GaI}_{1.5}$. It was powdered in a dry box and was extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet extractor for 3 days. The insoluble material left had a composition close to GaI (Found: Ga, 33.9; I, 64.1. Calc. Ga, 35.4; I, 64.5).

Preparation of Gallium Sulphide.— Ga_2S_3 was prepared by passing H_2S over gallium metal at 800° . It was reduced to GaS with hydrogen at 825° (Found: Ga, 67.7; Calc. 68.5%).

Preparation of the Complexes:

METHOD 1.—A calculated quantity of the ligand in benzene was added to a measured volume of a saturated solution of GaI_3 in benzene in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen. The complexes were immediately precipitated and filtered on a sintered glass filter, which was an integral part of the preparation apparatus.

The precipitate was washed with dry benzene and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The yields were quantitative.

METHOD 2.—For volatile ligands, the ligand was placed in a small bulb and suspended over a solution of gallium di-iodide in dry benzene. Over three days a precipitate was slowly formed in the solution. It was filtered, washed with benzene, and dried. The yields were quantitative. The compounds are documented in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	Method of Prep'n.	Gallium %		Iodine %		M.W. (nitrobenzene)		Molar conduct. at $10^{-3}M$. (mhos). 20°
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Anisole})_4$	1	12.7	12.9	47.6	47.0	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Acac})_2$	1	16.2	16.4	60.6	61.2	—	—	20.1
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Bzac})_2$	1	15.4	14.7	52.6	53.5	520	485	21.3
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Diox})_2$	1	16.9	16.9	61.2	61.6	460	411	21.2
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Sal. Ald.})_2$	1	16.1	16.2	59.2	59.0	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Aniline})_4$	1	14.2	14.5	53.4	53.1	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Py})_4$	2	14.2	14.4	52.0	52.7	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Sal. Ox})_2$	1	15.5	15.4	56.3	56.2	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Morph})_2$	1	16.9	16.9	61.2	61.4	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Dith.})_2$	1	11.9	12.0	43.4	43.8	—	—	21.2
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Eth. Morph})_1$	1	16.2	16.2	59.2	59.8	—	—	22.6
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_4$	2	15.5	15.7	56.6	56.6	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Pr}_2\text{S})_4$	2	13.8	13.3	45.3	44.9	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Ph}_2\text{S})_4$	1	10.0	10.7	36.5	36.0	—	—	—
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Bzac})_2$	3	15.2	14.7	51.2	53.5	—	—	21.0
$\text{Ga}_2\text{I}_4(\text{Morph})_2$	3	17.2	16.9	59.8	61.4	—	—	—

Subject to about 10% error on account of low solubility, making depressions only about 0.1°C .

Abbreviations: Acac—acetylacetone; Bzac—benzoylacetone; Diox—dioxane; Sal. Ald—salicylaldehyde; Py—Pyridine; Sal. Ox—salicylaldoxime; Morph—Morpholine; Dith—Dithione; Eth. Morph 1,2 ethylene morpholine; Me_2S —dimethyl sulphide; Pr_2S —di-n-propyl sulphide; Ph_2S —diphenyl sulphide.

METHOD 3.—In attempts to prepare gallium monoiodide complexes, GaI was refluxed with ligands under nitrogen. Gallium metal was formed in all the reactions attempted. With benzoylacetone and with morpholine, small amounts of solid were obtained when the ligand was decanted and removed under vacuum. The products were washed with benzene and dried.

Analysis.—Analyses for gallium were carried out gravimetrically¹⁰ as gallium sesquioxide, and volumetrically by titration against E.D.T.A. using morin in UV light as indicator¹¹. Iodine analyses were carried out volumetrically with standard iodate solution¹² with carbon tetrachloride as the detector phase.

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